

The Influence of The Training Program on The Knowledge of Posyandu Cadres in The Department of Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and The Community of Binjai City

Ruri Aswansari^{1*}, Muhammad Isa Indrawan²

Magister Manajemen, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia

*E-mail Correspondence: rurip3am@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of training on knowledge among Posyandu cadres for employees of the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection (DP3AM) Service. This research was carried out at the Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) Binjai City. The type of research is associative quantitative. The sample in this study was 172 Posyandu Cadres from the Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection Service (DP3AM) of Binjai City. The sampling technique in this study used a random sampling technique from the entire population of 1205 people. The research results show that training has a significant influence on knowledge as shown by the t value of 16.606 > t table 1.653 and the P value of 0.000 < 0.05. This shows that improvements in training can increase the knowledge of Posyandu cadres at the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community (DP3AM) Service.

Keywords: training; knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

Efforts to monitor the growth and development of early childhood are primarily the family's task. This is because the family is the closest environment to the child who knows exactly the child's growth and development journey. Family is also the environment where children spend time. From the time a child is born, they first come into contact with family members. Children learn about their immediate environment starting from observing the behavior of family members, (World Health Organization, 2014). However, not all families can carry out the task of monitoring children's growth and development optimally. Business, lack of knowledge, and family socio-economic conditions can be factors that do not support efforts to monitor early childhood growth and development.

Therefore, so far monitoring of children's growth and development has been coordinated through the role of the community through the Posyandu program, (Item & Mangalik, 2021). The Posyandu program is carried out in each village by cadres who have been given knowledge and training by health workers in collaboration with the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM). The aim of using cadres as Posyandu implementers is to disseminate knowledge about health, especially child growth and development. Generally, Posyandu activities include weighing toddlers and providing nutrition, so that the main target of Posyandu is more focused on the physical growth stage only (Hayati & Fatimaningrum, 2017). According to the results of the problem identification carried out regarding posyandu activities by the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM), the Posyandu activities

carried out so far are still monotonous and there are still few cadres. So, given these problems, we intend to carry out research with the aim of increasing the capacity of Posyandu cadres through the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM).

Cadre capacity is the quality or ability that cadres need to have in carrying out their duties at Posyandu. Various types of qualities that are included in the abilities and capacities of cadres include knowledge, attitudes, practical skills, performance or performance, self-confidence or self-efficacy, motivation, awareness, and so on. In order to increase cadre capacity, there are various efforts that can be carried out through various methods, (Suwarni & Ocrisyana, 2020). Capacity building can take the form of mentoring methods, providing education, increasing cadre skills in utilizing and processing local food, health communication about stunting, and cooperation between cadres in efforts to prevent and control stunting incidents in work areas. Apart from that, basic training for Posyandu cadres, regular cadre refresher training, and health promotion training can also be efforts to increase cadre capacity (Setyaningsih et al., 2021).

Many factors can influence the level of employee knowledge, one of which is training programs and managerial competence. According to (Sari, 2018) Training is all efforts to provide, improve and maintain work skills, product output, attitudes and ethics at certain levels of ability and skills, in accordance with the standards and qualifications of positions and jobs. A process for obtaining and improving a person's training and increasing the productivity of an employee. Training is part of the process of increasing human capital capital that can support organizational goals (Wibowo et al., 2019).

Training is an ongoing cycle and not just a temporary process, especially because technology and skills are growing rapidly to this day, the role of training or education plays a very important role in equipping workers to be more innovative in achieving company targets effectively and efficiently. Training is a process to improve employee competency and can train employees' abilities, skills, expertise and knowledge in order to carry out work effectively and efficiently to achieve goals in a company (Wahyuningsih, 2019).

According to (Wahyuningsih, 2019). There are 5 indicators in training, namely:

1) Training Objectives

Training objectives must be realistic and can be delivered in such a way that training is carried out to develop work skills so that participants can increase awareness of the work that participants must do.

2) Material

In the form of work management, essays, work correspondence, work psychology, work discipline and ethics, as well as work reporting, teaching materials can be used.

3) Method used

In training, the method used is teaching with a participatory approach such as group discussions, seminars, exercises, practice (demonstrations) and games, educational events, tests, group work visits and studies (comparative studies).

4) Participant Qualifications

Participants are employees who have passed the qualification requirements, such as permanent employees and employees with recommendations from leaders.

5) Coach qualifications

Trainers/providers of training to participants must meet qualification requirements such as: having skills related to the training material, being able to generate inspiration and motivation in participants and using participatory methods.

Knowledge is a very important domain for the formation of one's actions. Knowledge is the result of human sensing, or the result of a person's knowledge of objects through the senses they have (eyes, nose, ears, and some of them). The time from sensing to producing knowledge is greatly influenced by the intensity of perception of the object. Most of a person's knowledge is obtained through the sense of hearing (ears) and the sense of sight (eyes), (Albunsyary et al., 2020). Knowledge is the result of knowing, and this occurs after people sense a particular object. Sensing occurs through the five human senses, namely the senses of sight, hearing, smell, taste and touch. Knowledge Indicators namely Knowledge Indicators according to (Albunsyary et al., 2020) are as follows:

- 1) Know (know). This is the lowest level of knowledge which is defined as remembering material that has been studied previously to measure that people know about something by using verbs including mention, define, describe and so on.
- 2) Understanding (comprehension). It is the ability to explain correctly about known objects and be able to interpret the material correctly. If we understand the object, then we have to explain, explain, give examples, conclude and predict the object being studied.
- 3) Application (application). It is the ability to use material that has been studied in actual situations and conditions.
- 4) Analysis (analysis). It is the ability to describe material or objects into certain components, but within the organizational structure and have a relationship with each other.
- 5) Synthesis (synthesis). Demonstrates an ability to place or connect parts into a new whole.
- 6) Evaluation (evaluating). Is the ability to conduct research on a material or object based on predetermined criteria. After people gain knowledge, they then give rise to an inner response in the form of an attitude that they know. To reach agreement or a common perception so that confidence grows in the problems faced, a mature motivational communication-information process is needed, so that changes in one's behavior are expected to occur.

The purpose of this research is to analyze and determine the effect of training on employee knowledge in Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection Service (DP3AM). The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODS

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research. This research was carried out in Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection Service (DP3AM). This research was carried out from March to April 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) Population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study were all posyandu cadres Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM), totaling 1205 people with the following details:

Table 1. Total Population

Subdistrict	Number of Posyandu	Number of Cadres
North Binjai	58	290
South Binjai	40	200
East Binjai	59	295
West Binjai	38	190
Binjai City	46	230
Total	241	1205

In formulating the research sample, the Slovin formula was used as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Information:

n = Sample size/number of respondents

N = Population size

e = Percentage of allowance for sampling accuracy that can still be tolerated;

e = 0.1

In the Slovin formula there are the following provisions:

The value of e = 0.1 (10%) for large populations

The value of e = 0.2 (20%) for small populations

So, the sample range that can be taken from the Solvin technique is between 10-20% of the research population. The total population in this study was 186 employees, so the percentage of allowance used was 10% and the calculation results could be rounded to achieve suitability. So to find out the research sample, use the following calculations:

$$n = \frac{1205}{1 + 1205(0,05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1205}{1 + 1205(0,0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{1205}{1 + 6,025}$$

$$n = \frac{1205}{7,025}$$

$$n = 171.53 = 172$$

Based on the calculations above, the sample of respondents in this study was adjusted to 172 people, this was done to make data processing easier and for better test results. The samples taken were based on probability sampling techniques; simple random sampling, where the researcher provides an equal opportunity for each member of the population to be selected as a random sample without paying attention to the strata in the population itself. Details of the sample in this study can be seen as follows:

Table 2. Number of Samples

Subdistrict	Total Population	Number of Samples
North Binjai	290	41
South Binjai	200	29
East Binjai	295	42
West Binjai	190	27
Binjai City	230	33
Total	1205	172

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all posyandu cadres. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0. Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable. The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Knowledge

X = Training

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) The determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely training (X), on the dependent variable, namely knowledge (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable

(Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research results

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest scores, rating score and standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Training	172	2.00	5.00	4.1372	,67591
Knowledge	172	2.67	5.00	4.1491	,55384
Valid N (listwise)	172				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents rated the Training and Knowledge at the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) as above average, with mean values of 4.137 and 4.149 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.675 for training and 0.553 for knowledge), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Training Program Variables (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
PEL1	0.750 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PEL2	0.657 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PEL3	0.622 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PEL4	0.741 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PEL5	0.631 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above, it can be stated that the indicators for the Training variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.149 with a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05, so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Training variable are valid. (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Table 4. Validity Test Results for Knowledge Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
PENG1	0.467 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PENG2	0.748 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PENG3	0.498 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PENG4	0.540 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PENG5	0.440 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
PENG6	0.763 > 0.149	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators in the Knowledge variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.149 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for the Knowledge variable are valid. (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) reliability testing aims to measure how reliable or trustworthy the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (α) value is > 0.61 .

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Training	0.709	5
Knowledge	0.611	6

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (α) value of the Training and Knowledge variable is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1,483	,163		9,114	,000
Training	,644	,039	,787	16,606	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Knowledge

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 1.483 + 0.644X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 1.483 means that if there is no training, then there is knowledge of 1.483 points. The Training regression coefficient is 0.644, meaning that Training influences an increase in Knowledge of 0.644 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 7. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,787a	,619	,616	,34303

a. Predictors: (Constant), Training

The test results in table 7 show an Adjusted R Square value of 0.616 or 61.60%, which means that training has a high influence on knowledge, while the remaining 48.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of training on knowledge among posyandu cadres of the Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection (DP3AM) Service

Ha: There is an influence of training on knowledge among posyandu cadres of the Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection Service (DP3AM) of Binjai City

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 8. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1,483	,163		9,114	,000
Training	,644	,039	,787	16,606	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Knowledge

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $16.606 > t$ table 1.653, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted or there is a positive and significant influence between Training on Knowledge at the Women's Empowerment, Protection Service Children and Communities (DP3AM) Binjai City.

Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of training on the knowledge of Posyandu cadres, this finding is in line with the research results (Arianto, 2022) which shows that nutritional knowledge of toddler posyandu cadres in Nyalindung District before and after being given training ($p=0.057$) and there was a change in the skill level of toddler posyandu cadres in Nyalindung District before and after being given training ($p=0.0001$). This means that improvements in training can contribute to increasing Managerial Competence, which then has an impact on increasing Posyandu Cadre Knowledge.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of the research data analysis and discussion described above, it can be concluded that training has a significant influence on the knowledge of posyandu cadres in Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) with t count of $16.606 > t$ table 1.653, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. These results indicate that if training is improved, cadres' knowledge tends to increase.

The adjusted R Square value is 0.616 or 61.60%, which means that training has a moderate influence on knowledge, while the remaining 48.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. Overall, this research provides insight into the importance of factors such as training in influencing the knowledge of Posyandu cadres in Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child and Community Protection Service (DP3AM).

Suggestion

Based on the results of the research, discussion and conclusions obtained, suggestions that can be given are: the Training and Knowledge variables need to be maintained and improved. Therefore, The Binjai City Women's Empowerment, Child Protection and Community Service (DP3AM) should increase training for posyandu cadres. The training provided must also be more diverse because with diverse training it will also be possible to increase the knowledge of posyandu cadres.

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